

Assessing the Relative Probability of a Zoonosis or Lab-Leak as the Origin of the SARS-CoV-2 Pandemic

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Abstract

While there has been significant public debate on the origins of SARS-CoV-2, the scientific debate has been unusually subdued. Members of the scientific community have often stated that a zoonosis is a more likely explanation, yet these assertions are either stated without justification or from individuals with apparent conflicts of interest. Here, the available evidence is considered and conservative probability estimates are used, and it is found that a Lab leak is more likely than a Zoonosis. This determination rests on conservative probability assessments of: 1) the prior probability of a lab leak vs zoonosis, 2) the apparent location of emergence, 3) the circumstances of emergence indicating no link to a wet market, 4) the timing of emergence, 5) the fitness of the virus upon emergence, 6) the presence of a SARS-CoV-2 precursor being present in a lab prior to the pandemic, 7) the relative risk of spillover due to known research practices near the apparent site of emergence, and 8) the relative risk of a SARS-related viruses leaking from a lab or emerging from zoonosis. Statements by members of the scientific community to the public that a lab leak is unlikely, without actually carrying out an analysis of the likelihood or from persons with serious potential conflicts of interests, are irresponsible and may severely damage the reputation of the scientific community. Such statements should be aggressively challenged.

Introduction

Since the emergence of SARS-CoV-2, there has been considerable debate over the origins of the virus. Two competing explanations have been put forth, a natural spillover event from bats to humans (possibly through an intermediate species)[1], and as a result of a lab leak. Due to the lack of direct evidence for either hypothesis, both are rather vague and cover many different scenarios

The Lab Leak hypothesis

The “Lab Leak” hypothesis contemplates many possible scenarios. At one end of the spectrum, the spillover event is simply the result of lab personnel being infected during sampling activities of a natural reservoir. At the other end of the spectrum the laboratory would be more involved in the creation of the virus itself, through studies designed to result in spillovers or creation of chimeric viruses for legitimate scientific purposes. It is important to note that consideration of a lab leak scenario is not an accusation of malice or gross negligence.

Emergence of SARS-CoV-2

In late 2019, a novel coronavirus began spreading in humans, and the first transmission events were detected in Wuhan[2].

Among the earliest cases, there were many cases with no significant link to the Wuhan animal market, and no RNA sequences matching SARS-CoV-2 were found in food or animals there[3,4]. In contrast, when SARS-CoV-1 emerged, there was extensive infection of multiple species of animals at the Guangdong wet market[5]. Furthermore, the SARS-CoV-2 had already split into the A and B lineages prior to the outbreak

at the Wuhan wetmarket[3], with the wetmarket outbreak being from lineage B, which is derived from the ancestral A[6,7]. Taken together, this establishes that the Wuhan wet market was not the source of the outbreak, and the animal to human leap did not occur there, which is a position advanced in the WHO origins report and by Shi Zengli of the WIV[4]. The closest published animal CoV sequence, RaTG13, originates from the Yunnan province[2], roughly 1,500 km away. For comparison, SARS-CoV-1 first emerged in a Guangdong wet market which was approximately 1000 kilometers away from the animal reservoir of the closest known related virus, which had a much higher (99.8%) sequence match[5].

So far, studies of coronaviruses in wild bat populations have not found evidence of higher circulation of CoVs within bat populations during winter/December (when they are hibernating in the region) [8–10].

A relatively high level of negative or relaxed selection pressure and high transmissibility were observed even in the earliest SARS-CoV-2 cases[3,11,12]. In contrast, a strong positive selection and rapid adaptation was observed in the SARS-CoV-1 outbreaks[13]. This has led to the conclusion that there was a period of adaptation to humans before the outbreak in the Wuhan Market [3,14,15]. This adaptation could have taken place through an intermediate host naturally, through agricultural practices, or in a lab. In all non-lab related scenarios, one would expect that there existed a number of intermediates variants with a transmissibility that was likewise intermediate between a virus like RaTG13 or SARS-CoV-1 and the very contagious earliest known SARS-CoV-2 variants. So far such intermediates have not been identified.

Probability calculations

The probability of a lab leak vs zoonosis event will be determined by estimating the prior probability of a lab leak vs zoonosis event, and then assessing the relative probability of obtaining the observed results under a lab leak or zoonosis scenario.

Prior Probability estimation:

P_b = basal ratio of the probability of a lab leak vs zoonosis event for a pandemic virus

P_{SARS} = modifier for ratio of the probability of a lab leak vs zoonosis event for a SARS-related virus

P_{SARS-2} = probability of the presence of a suitable SARS-CoV-2 precursor in a lab prior to the pandemic

P_{LP} = modifier for ratio of the probability of a lab leak vs zoonosis event given certain lab practices

P_p = the ratio of the prior probability of a lab leak vs a zoonotic event for the origin of SARS-CoV-2

The prior probability of a lab leak vs zoonosis event for a SARS-related virus cannot be determined experimentally, and must be estimated. Even the basal probability of a lab leak vs zoonosis event cannot be determined experimentally. Using past statistics is one possible way to arrive at an estimate, but it is vulnerable to bias in selecting categories to be included or excluded (viruses vs any pathogen, any outbreak vs pandemic outbreaks, outbreak size cut-offs, etc.). All prior known lab leaks come from pathogens with identified precursors so the probability of such a precursor being present in a laboratory must be incorporated into a prior probability estimate. Furthermore, the specific characteristics of SARS-related viruses may differ from the wider group of pathogens or viruses, and the prior probability estimate should be adjusted to account for these specifics. Lastly, the probability of a lab leak is heavily dependent upon lab practices, and the prior probability estimate must take these into account as well.

The *prior probability* ratio will thus be estimated as follows: $P_p = P_b \times P_{SARSr} \times P_{SARS-2} \times P_{LP}$

Estimate of P_b , the basal probability ratio

Currently only one viral pandemic, the 1977 H1N1 flu pandemic, is widely accepted as the result of a lab leak[16]. There have been numerous other lab leaks of pathogens and viruses, although most lead to only small outbreaks. During this time, there have been numerous zoonotic events, such as the emergence of SARS-CoV-1, but these have been of varying size, and few have reached pandemic proportions (HIV, various flu strains, etc.). To avoid the risk of being too restrictive, a very conservative estimate of 1:100 (with the basal probability of a zoonosis event being 100x more likely than a lab leak) will be used in these calculations.

Estimate of P_{SARSr} , the probability adjustment for SARS-related viruses

Currently, there have been two documented cases of SARS-virus zoonotic events, the 2002 and 2003 outbreaks. In contrast there have been 5 documented escapes from labs (Sep. 2003 in Singapore; Dec. 2003 in Taiwan; 2x Apr. 2004 in China, and May 2004 in China) [17–20]. Thus suggests a 2.5:1 ratio and not a 1:100 ratio, or a risk 250 fold higher than the basal estimate, based on available data. Despite this, there is likely a reporting bias, with small infection chains from lab leaks being detected at much higher rates than zoonosis events. Indeed, in 2012, there was likely a SARS-related zoonosis event in the Mojiang mine[21]. There have likely been numerous unreported minor transmission chains in addition to the 2002 and 2003 outbreaks. Therefore, a very conservative modifier of 2 will be used, rather than 250. $P_b \times P_{SARSr}$ is thus 1:50.

Estimate of P_{SARS-2} , the probability of a suitable SARS-2 precursor being present in a lab

While no sequence similar to SARS-CoV-2 had been published prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, the closest known virus, RaTG13, had been collected in 2013 and was only described in 2020. It is very common for sequences to go unpublished for several years, and the WIV's database of unpublished sequences, which has been taken offline, is believed to be quite extensive. Its collection of samples is likely even more extensive, as samples may be present for years before proper sequencing is done.

It is known that the WIV extensively sampled the specific cave (on multiple occasions) from which RaTG13 was found, which is a SARS-CoV-2 related virus. This virus was identified as being of particular interest in a 2016 publication[22]. The virus is also linked to a location from which a probable lethal viral pneumonia was found[21], making it of particular relevance to the WIV's mission. Furthermore, the anomalously low bacterial read content of the published WGS (Figure 1) suggests that either special sample preparation methods were employed, or the sample was of a special type (ie, not a fecal swab as claimed). Thus it can be said with high confidence that the WIV was extensively taking samples in areas containing the clade to which SARS-CoV-2 belongs, and paid special attention to this clade.

A search of the Chinese government database (<http://www.preintell.cn/nsfc/search/>) reveals a project number (批准号) 31800142, which is a 2018 project titled: "Pathogenicity of two new bat SARS-related coronaviruses to transgenic mice expressing human ACE2" (两株新型蝙蝠SARS相关冠状病毒对表达人ACE2的转基因小鼠的致病性研究). The applicant (申请单位) is listed as Wuhan Institute of Virology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (中国科学院武汉病毒研究所). SARS-CoV-2 is aptly described as a "new bat SARS-related coronavirus" which would be pathogenic to "transgenic mice expressing human ACE2". Such

a description prior to the naming of SARS-CoV-2, indicates that it is plausible that SARS-CoV-2 related precursors were present at WIV prior to the outbreak. Despite this, with no direct evidence, a conservative estimate of a 20% chance (1:5) will be used.

$P_b \times P_{SARSr} \times P_{SARS-2}$ is thus $1/100 \times 2/1 \times 1/5 = 1/250$. That is, a zoonotic event is considered 250 times more likely than a lab leak, prior to factoring in observations about the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak and the lab practices in Wuhan.

Estimate P_{LP} , the modifier for lab practices

It is readily apparent that the probability of a lab leak is zero with no practicing labs, and will be much higher if a lab is engaged in research involving infection with live virus, as opposed to surrogate pseudoviruses or simple sequencing reactions. Based on numerous sources, including the obvious implications of a project titled “Pathogenicity of two new bat SARS-related coronaviruses to transgenic mice expressing human ACE2”, as well as the project description listed here: <https://reporter.nih.gov/project-details/9491676> make it clear that the WIV was engaged in research involving infected animals with live SARS-related virus strains. In contrast to cell culture, animals move around, create aerosols, and potentially bite. Similarly, collection activities (part of lab practice) present similar risks, and have been reported to result in bites and being covered in blood spatter (<https://nypost.com/2021/05/28/scientists-at-wuhan-lab-filmed-being-bitten-by-bats-report/>). The use of live virus in animals greatly increases the spillover risk, and will conservatively be assigned a modifier of 2.

In addition to this, the use of humanized mice further increases the risk of spillover to humans, and will conservatively be estimated to increase the P_{LP} modifier by another factor of 2 to arrive at a factor of 4.

Lastly, it is evident from project descriptions (<https://reporter.nih.gov/project-details/9819304>) that the WIV was engaged in research that would expressly conduct *in vivo* infections with infectious virus to test predicted determinants of spillover potential. An obvious predictable outcome of such tests is that the virus spills over into the test subjects, and indeed would seem to be a goal of such research. Therefore the modifier estimate will be conservatively increased by another factor of 2.

P_{LP} is thus considered to be 8.

In summary, the described research projects would be expected to result in spillover of the virus into a new host, with that new host being a live animal rather than cultured cells, and that live animal would be a humanized animal. Indeed, this is not only expected, but confirmed by the 2018 project description, which clearly indicates pathogenic infections of humanized mice by 2 distinct SARS-related coronaviruses.

In considering all these factors, using an estimate for the increase in risk of a lab leak that is less than an order of magnitude seems very conservative.

Using these conservative estimates, the prior probability is thus estimated to be as follows:

$P_D = P_b \times P_{SARSr} \times P_{SARS-2} \times P_{LP} = 1/100 \times 2/1 \times 1/5 \times 8/1 = 4/125$. That is, the probability ratio of a lab leak to zoonotic event is considered to be 4:125 (thus a natural spillover is approximately 31 times more likely), prior to factoring in observations about the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak and the lab practices in Wuhan.

Posterior probability modifiers

After the outbreak, observations have been made about the location of the outbreak, circumstances of the outbreak, timing in relation to lab activity, and the initial fitness of the virus. All of these observations about the virus are unexpected to different degrees, and can be used to arrive at a posterior probability estimates for the relative likelihood of lab leak vs zoonotic scenarios.

Posterior Probability calculations

P_L = relative probability of the outbreak happening in the observed location

P_c = relative probability of the outbreak happening under the observed circumstances

P_{fit} = relative probability of the initial virus having the observed fitness circumstances

P_t = relative probability of the outbreak happening at the observed time

Posterior probability will thus be estimated as follows: $P_{post} = P_p \times P_L \times P_c \times P_{fit} \times P_t$

Estimate P_L , the probability of the observed location of emergence

It has been argued that it is not implausible that Wuhan was the apparent location of an outbreak given the city's size and trade connections. It must be noted that the city is the 9th largest in China, with a population estimate of approximately 8,350,000 people. This is only 6.1% of the combined population of the 10 largest Chinese cities (thus about 1:16 residents of the 10 largest cities in China are from Wuhan), and 4.2% of the 20 largest (less than 1:20 residents of the 20 largest Chinese cities are from Wuhan). Notably, the closest identified viruses come from the Yunnan province, near the Chinese border, and roughly 1,500 km away from Wuhan. Distance to the most likely animal reservoirs should be taken into account (indeed, it must be if the population of every city in the world is not to be included when assessing the probability that Wuhan would be the city where it apparently emerges), as should the population of nearby cities of neighboring countries such as Hanoi in Vietnam.

It is also worth noting that the two prior zoonotic events of SARS both took place in cities in the Guangdong province, with the 2003 outbreak occurring in a city that is both considerably larger and closer to the putative animal reservoir. Furthermore, Bat-CoV expert Shi Zhengli herself admitted that she never expected a novel coronavirus to breakout in Wuhan[4,23].

Thus based only on population of the 20 largest cities within China, Wuhan should be regarded as having a very low probability (less than 1:20) of being the apparent location of an outbreak under a zoonotic scenario. Factoring in distance to animal reservoirs and cities outside China that are closer to the animal reservoirs, the probability of an outbreak in Wuhan must be even lower. In contrast, an outbreak in Wuhan is highly probable under a lab leak scenario, given it is the world's leading coronavirus research institute and the largest repository of SARS-related CoV samples.

A very conservative relative probability estimate of 1:20 is thus used for P_L .

Estimate P_c , the probability of the observed circumstances of emergence

Through multiple lines of evidence, it is clear that the Wuhan wetmarket was an early super-spreader site, but not the site at which the virus first began spreading in humans. This evidence includes the Wetmarket cases belonging to only clade B, and evidence that clade A was closer to the ancestral virus. No evidence

of infected animals was found in the wetmarket frozen samples, or from sampling of farms supplying the market.

The two previous SARS-CoV-1 outbreaks were both linked to wetmarkets, with widespread detection of infections in animals being sold there. Thus there are 3 instances of a SARS related virus outbreak that is first detected in a major city, with only 2 linked to wet markets as the site of initial zoonosis.

There are of course ways for a natural spillover to happen outside of a city, but to only be detected after entry into the city – although it is somewhat unlikely that phylogenetics will show all cases have a transmission chain originating from the city, depending on the distance of the city to the animal reservoir (all transmission chains prior to entry into the city would have had to die out in this scenario).

Conservatively, if SARS-CoV-2 was the result of a natural zoonosis, this would make the 2/3 of the zoonoses linked to wet markets. In contrast, under a lab leak scenario the circumstances would not be expected to involve a wet market origin.

A conservative relative probability estimate of 1:3 is thus used for P_L .

Estimate P_t , the probability of the observed time of emergence

Under a natural zoonosis scenario, there was no particular reason for there to be an increased risk of zoonosis at the end of 2019. Population increases and further penetration into bat habitats are often cited as factors leading to a generally increasing yearly risk. If the risk of a zoonosis is presumed to be low each year (although slowly increasing), the risk can still be considerable over a number of years. Given the relatively few cases of SARS-related spillovers, a risk of approximately 1 spillover every 10 years on average seems conservative.

In contrast, a project funded in mid-2014 began with the stated goal of testing “predictions of CoV inter-species transmission” in various models including humanized mice as its 3rd aim (<https://reporter.nih.gov/project-details/8674931>). This project thus ran from its award date in May 2014, through the emergence of SARS-CoV-2, roughly 4.5 years. That a spillover would occur during this time window would seem to be an event with a roughly 1 in 2 chance of happening, if there are natural spillovers every 10 years on average, at the current risk rate. In contrast a Lab leak scenario would require that the spillover happens during a project such as this. There do not seem to be any other relevant projects testing interspecies transmission/spillover potential that were occurring outside this time frame for this to be a case of cherry-picking data. Indeed, restricting the time window to that seen in other projects (2018: “Pathogenicity of two new bat SARS-related coronaviruses to transgenic mice expressing human ACE2”) only makes this coincidence more unlikely.

Notably, the project that began in mid-2014 had the same description of the 3rd aim until the 2019 project description which altered the description of the 3rd aim, and added more detail (<https://reporter.nih.gov/project-details/9819304>). This strongly suggests that the spillover studies, planned since mid-2014 or earlier, began in 2019. The temporal association between the assumed start of spillover studies in humanized lab animals, and the spillover of SARS-CoV-2 into humans, seems to be somewhat unlikely in the event of a natural spillover event, but highly likely under a lab leak scenario.

Despite this, a conservative relative probability estimate of 1:2 will be used for the ratio of the probability of a natural spillover happening by mere coincidence at the same time as these projects with high spillover potential vs the probability of a lab leak happening during the timeframe of said projects.

2:1 is thus used for P_t , the probability ratio of a lab leak vs spillover, considering the time of emergence.

Estimate P_{fit} , the probability ratio of the observed fitness upon emergence

When a new SARS-related CoV emerges, one would expect on average 50% of them to be better adapted to humans than SARS-CoV-1 initially was, and 50% to be worse – that is a 1 in 2 chance of being more fit. By measures of transmissibility, hACEII affinity, positive and negative selection rates, it can be concluded that SARS-CoV-2 was substantially more fit than SARS-CoV-1 upon their respective emergences. Instead of being slightly more or less fit, it was observed that SARS-CoV-2 was substantially more fit for spread in humans, and this observation would not be expected under a natural spillover event. In contrast, it would be highly expected under many lab leak scenarios.

A very conservative relative probability estimate of 2:1 is thus used for P_{fit} , the probability ratio of a lab leak vs spillover, considering the fitness upon emergence.

Using these conservative estimates, the posterior probability is thus estimated to be as follows:

$$P_{post} = 4/125 \times 20/1 \times 3/1 \times 2/1 \times 2/1 = 960/125 = 7.68$$

Thus a conservative series of estimates leads to the conclusion that a lab leak is nearly 8 times as likely as a zoonosis event, given the available evidence.

Discussion

There is a dearth of data regarding the relative probabilities for a lab leak or a zoonotic event. Statistics of past events are not very useful, given the risks from research activities of the past differ greatly from the present risks. The probability estimates used here are thus composites of objective deductions and subjective assessments. Despite this, component estimates were made with the goal of being conservative (that is erring in favor of a natural spillover). There are likely many additional factors that can be used to adjust the prior and posterior probability estimates further.

It is likely that further analysis could be done to better constrain the factors that have been considered.

Additional factors not included in the probability estimate, but worthy of note include: the apparently discrepant statements by WIV researchers (either the RaTG13 samples were given special treatment, or were not in fact fecal swabs, either one contradicting public statements), misleading statements (particularly regarding the sequencing dates of RaTG13, and its connection to fatal cases that were initially described as viral pneumonias[3,21,24]), attempts to delete early sequence data which clarified that the outbreak did not begin in a wetmarket[7], initial attempts to cover-up the outbreak coupled with subsequent destruction of early SARS-CoV-2 samples and censoring of SARS-CoV-2 publications, refusal to turn over information on suspected earlier cases of SARS-CoV-2 or to allow a lab audit, and a majority of publications and public statements in support of a natural zoonosis event coming from individuals with conflicts of interest[1,25]. All these actions by various parties are suspicious and make more sense under a lab-leak scenario than under a natural zoonosis event.

It thus seems that in the absence of direct evidence, the circumstantial evidence strongly points towards a lab-leak.

Put another way, using very conservative estimates for the timing, location, and fitness at emergence, while considering the lab practices at the WIV, one would have to conclude that there was less than a 1 in 38 chance that the WIV was in possession of a suitable SARS-CoV-2 precursor, in order to conclude that a Lab Leak hypothesis is less likely than a natural spillover event. Given the extensive sampling that the WIV has been conducting for decades now, with a documented history of sampling locations where SARS-CoV-2 clade viruses were present (ie: RaTG13), and the documented presence of 2 novel SARS-related bat coronaviruses that cause pathogenic effects in mice expressing human Ace2, it does not seem that such a low probability of presence is supported by the data.

The analysis presented here illustrates that it cannot be assumed that a natural spillover is more likely than a lab leak, given the available data. The scientific community must engage in critical, peer reviewed evaluation of the available evidence before continuing to present the zoonosis scenario as the most likely explanation for the origin of SARS-CoV-2. Individuals with a connection to research labs in Wuhan, and thus severe conflicts of interest, cannot be allowed to become the public face of the scientific community.

If it is determined by entities other than the scientific community (such as whistleblowers or government intelligence agencies through espionage or other means) that SARS-CoV-2 is a result of a lab leak (as it seems probable that it is), the wider scientific community will be seen at best as incompetent and arrogant, and at worst as guilty co-conspirators and of a cover-up of one of the largest crimes in human history – with some members of the community being seen as guilty perpetrators. Such a loss of confidence would severely hamper the ability to combat the pandemic.

Conclusion

Circumstantial evidence, coupled with conservative estimates of various probabilities, strongly points towards a lab leak scenario. The scientific community urgently needs to engage in a frank evaluation of the available evidence, and should refrain from stating that a zoonosis event is more likely until such an evaluation is done by those without serious conflicts of interest. The credibility of the scientific community rests in the balance, and that credibility is desperately needed in order to control this pandemic and get the public to follow proper scientific guidance.

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